

कृण्वन्तो विश्वमार्यम्

यतेमहि स्वराज्ये

ISSN : 2228-7227

Year : 9

Issue : 34 (III)

April - June 2019

www.chintanresearchjournal.com

Impact factor : 4.012

International Refereed

चिन्तन

Chintan
Research Journal

रिसर्च जर्नल

(कला, साहित्य, मानविकी, समाज-विज्ञान, विधि, प्रबंधन, वाणिज्य एवं विज्ञान विषयों पर केंद्रित)

(Indexed & Listed at : Ulrich's Periodicals Directory ©, ProQuest . U.S.A.)

(Indexed & Listed at : Copernicus, Poland)

(Indexed & Listed at : Research Bib, Japan)

(indexed & Listed at : Indian Journal Index (IJINDEX))

(UGC Approved List No. 41243)

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आचार्य (डॉ०) शीलक राम

यावत् जीवेत् सुखं जीवेत्

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ISO 9001 : 2008

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A Brief Report on Archaeological Explorations in Gohana Tehsil, District Sonipat, Haryana

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Abstract

This paper is a initial report of village-to-village survey of Gohana Tehsil, Sonipat district, Haryana. One hundred and fifteen archaeological sites were documented during the exploration in July and August 2018. Out of them thirty-eight new archaeological were documented in this survey. The purpose of this project is to get general information for my Ph.D. Research work about archaeological sites in the area. Results of this survey will solve many problems such as settlement's size, geo-coordinates etc.

Key Words: Field Work, Archaeological Sites, Pottery, Antiquities.

Introduction

The study area lies in the south-eastern part of Haryana. The area is rich in archaeological remains and the fact it has been proved by the explorations conducted by various scholars. The credit for initiating archaeological field work goes to some researcher like Dr. Sliak Ram, Dr. Suraj Bhan, Dr. Dutt, Mr. Dhankar, Dr. R.C. Thakran and Vinay Kumar.

Dr. Sliak Ram Carried out explorations for their Ph.D. work in Rohtak and Hisar District of Haryana and reported some sites. Some sculptures and many more¹. After some time in 1975 Dr. Suraj Bhan also carried out an exploration for their Ph.D. work and brought to light some new sites². Dr. Dutt also explored the area in 1980 for the work on topic PGW in Haryana³. After that Mr. Dhankar explored Gohana Block for the same purpose and found some new Archaeological sites⁴. Later Dr. R.C. Thakran Carried out explorations in South-Eastern Haryana and reported some new Archaeological sites. Some sculptures and many more⁵. Dr. Vinay Kumar also did the archaeological exploration in some part of the study area and brought to light some new site in special reference to Gohana Block⁶. With this archaeological background present researcher commence the village-to-village survey in Sonipat district, Haryana.

Drainage system

The Sonipat region suffers from poor drainage and this problem is also present in some parts of the Gohana Tehsil. Due to poor surface drainage and abundant ancient canal system, the water table is very high. The general slope of the area from north to south. The area under study is part of the Yamuna River Plain. It is made of wearables. The Yamuna River originates from the Yamunotri Glacier. The river flows through the states of Uttarakhnad, Himachal Pradesh, Haryana and Delhi before the confluence of the Ganges River in Allahabad, Uttar Pradesh. The total length of this holy river is about 1,376 km⁷.

Methodology

- 1) The present researcher conducted a comprehensive survey from village-to-village in the area.
- 2) A GPS Device (Garmin, GPSSmap 60CSx) was used to record correct co-ordinates of the sites.
- 3) Pottery and other residues were sampled from the surface and exposed to suitable sections.
- 4) Based on detailed analysis of environmental conditions and ancient settlements, various categories such as regional centers, villages, industrial centers and camp sites have been identified. The main focus is on identifying sites and observing patterns of distribution of cultural remains in the area. The dating of the sites was determined based on the occurrence of clinical ceramic forms of ancient cultures. The size of the sites was estimated based on the area in which the cultural reserves were found.
- 5) Cultural material discovered from the survey and housed in different museums was analyzed and studied to address the problems.
- 6) The available published literature and survey reports including unpublished Thesis/ dissertations were examined and their data was also included in this study. Following table 1 is the list of sites explored by researchers:

Table 1 Showing explored sites along with geo-references, previous work and cultural sequence.

Sr.No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (EK)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
1.	Ahmadpur Mazra	29°13'33.2"	76°42'00.3"	3	New	Med.
2.	Ahulana-1	29°07'06.6"	76°39'24.9"	3	New	His.
3.	Ahulana-2	29°07'08.0"	76°38'12.4"	2	New	His.
4.	Anwali-1	29°00'06.1"	76°46'59.5"	4	New	Med.
5.	Anwali-2	28°59'54.7"	76°45'27.5"	10	R.C.Thakran	RW, E.Med.
6.	Bajana Kalan	29°09'33.0"	76°50'29.6"	4	New	His. Med.
7.	Bali	29°03'31.9"	76°44'24.6"	3	Sliak Ram, R.C.Thakran, Vinay Kumar	His (RW), Med.
8.	Banwasa-1	29°08'34.8"	76°33'43.9"	4	New	Med.
9.	Banwasa-2	29°09'16.2"	76°33'44.0"	3	New	LMH, LH, His.
10.	Banwasa-3	29°08'33.0"	76°34'25.7"	15	R.C.Thakran	LH.
11.	Baroda Mor-1	29°09'31.7"	76°35'38.1"	4	New	His. Med.
12.	Baroda Mor-2	29°08'53.7"	76°35'18.3"	6	Gulab Singh, R.C.Thakran	MH, LH, PGW, His (L. Kusana, rang Mehal Type), Med.
13.	Baroda Thuthan-1	29°08'34.0"	76°37'31.4"	15	R.C.Thakran	LMH, LH, His. Med.
14.	Baroda Thuthan-2	29°07'05.2"	76°37'13.0"	4	R.C.Thakran	EH, MH, LH, PGW.
15.	Barota-1	29°07'19.8"	76°44'12.3"	10	New	Med.
16.	Barota-2	29°07'20.5"	76°44'33.2"	6	R.C.Thakran, Vinay Kumar	LH, OCP, PGW, His (RW), Med
17.	Bhainswal Kalan -1	29°01'59.7"	76°47'01.9"	4	New	Med.
18.	Bhainswal Kalan-2	29°02'16.4"	76°48'04.7"	10	Vinay Kumar	LH, His.
19.	Bhainswal Kalan-3	29°00'55.8"	76°47'00.4"	10	Vinay Kumar	Med.
20.	Bhainswan	29°05'02.7"	76°39'54.0"	2	Vinay Kumar	His.
21.	Bhathotri	29°14'26.3"	76°45'28.0"	10	R.C.Thakran	LMH, LH, His (RW), Med.
22.	Bhawar-1	29°12'11.6"	76°31'21.0"	3	Ashok Kumar, Ram, Sliak R.C.Thakran	LH, PGW, His (RW), Med.

23.	Bhawar-2	29°12'28.5"	76°30'13.3"	2	R.C.Thakran	MH, LH, His, Med.
24.	Bibbiliana	29°00'06.1"	76°46'59.5"	15	R.C.Thakran	LH, His (RW), E. Med.
25.	Bichpari-1	29°13'07.4"	76°38'43.0"	2	Gujab Singh, Bhan, R.C.Thakran	LH.
26.	Bichpari-2	29°12'40.3"	76°39'41.1"	6	New	His.
27.	Bidhal-1	29°04'38.2"	76°48'25.8"	10	Vinay Kumar	LH, OCP.
28.	Bidhal-2	29°04'02.7"	76°48'22.3"	2	R.C.Thakran	MH, LH, His, Med.
29.	Butana	29°12'19.3"	76°34'24.4"	4	Gujab Singh, Ram, R.C.Thakran	His.
30.	Busana Kalan	29°14'07.4"	76°44'14.2"	4	R.C.Thakran	LH, PGW.
31.	Chhapra-1	29°07'35.0"	76°33'00.2"	2	New	His, Med.
32.	Chhapra-2	29°07'56.8"	76°32'22.2"	5	Ashok Kumar, Ram, R.C.Thakran	LH, PGW(BSW), His (RW, NBPW), Med.
33.	Chhatehra-1	29°14'46.2"	76°42'31.7"	2	New	LH, OCP, PGW
34.	Chhatehra-2	29°13'56.2"	76°42'29.5"	15	Gujab Singh	His, Med.
35.	Chichrana	29°04'02.7"	76°38'03.2"	2	New	PGW.
36.	Dhanana	29°06'39.4"	76°30'34.6"	4	R.C.Thakran	His.
37.	Dhurana	29°13'42.3"	76°47'00.1"	3	Silak Ram	His.
38.	Gamri-1	29°08'34.4"	76°46'27.8"	5	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
39.	Gamri-2	29°09'27.6"	76°46'21.0"	5	New	His, Med.
40.	Gangana-1	29°12'19.3"	76°37'23.7"	3	Gujab Singh, Bhan, Sural	LH, His.
41.	Gangana-2	29°14'11.2"	76°37'58.0"	3	R.C.Thakran	MH, LH.
42.	Gangeshar-1	29°11'13.6"	76°40'29.7"	7	R.C.Thakran	LH, PGW(BSW), His, Med.
43.	Gangeshar-2	29°11'56.7"	76°40'44.9"	4	Gujab Singh, R.C.Thakran	EH, MH, LH.
44.	Garhi	29°08'16.5"	76°42'38.4"	7	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
45.	Garhi Ujala Khan	29°08'26.4"	76°43'04.7"	3	Vinay Kumar	Med.
46.	Gharwal-1	29°11'17.8"	76°33'57.3"	6	Silak Ram, R.C.Thakran	EH, MH, LH, His, Med.
47.	Gharwal-2	29°09'20.8"	76°31'21.5"	6	Silak Ram, R.C.Thakran	LH, LH, His.
48.	Gharwal-3	29°10'09.6"	76°33'08.1"	10	Ashok Kumar, Ram, Silak R.C.Thakran	EH, MH, LH, PGW(BSW), His, Med.
49.	Giwana-1	28°58'33.0"	76°44'14.0"	3	New	His.
50.	Giwana-2	28°58'28.0"	76°45'00.0"	4	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
51.	Gudha	29°07'26.2"	76°40'41.5"	15	New	His, Med.
52.	Isapur Kheri	29°12'42.9"	76°35'50.3"	5	Gujab Singh, R.C.Thakran	LH, GW.
53.	Jagsi-1	29°12'45.9"	76°39'43.8"	4	R.C.Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
54.	Jagsi-2	29°12'17.0"	76°39'14.5"	5	New	LH, His.
55.	Jauli-1	29°06'16.3"	76°48'06.5"	2	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
56.	Jauli-2	29°05'38.2"	76°43'00.9"	3	Vinay Kumar	Med.
57.	Jawahara-1	29°15'35.8"	76°47'21.3"	3	R.C.Thakran	LH, PGW, His.
58.	Jawahara-2	29°15'11.0"	76°47'50.6"	3	R.C.Thakran	His (RW).
59.	Kailana Khaa-1	29°10'37.3"	76°46'21.4"	4	New	His, Med.
60.	Kailana Khaa-2	29°10'11.6"	76°45'53.7"	6	Silak Ram, R.C.Thakran, Vinay Kumar	EH, LH, GW, His (RW), E. Med.
61.	Kakana	29°08'13.5"	76°48'38.8"	10	Dhankar, R.C.Thakran, Vinay Kumar	LH, PGW, His (RW), Med.
62.	Kasanda	29°08'06.5"	76°49'54.0"	3	Vinay Kumar	Med.
63.	Kasandi-1	29°08'58.3"	76°50'23.3"	5	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
64.	Kasandi-2	29°08'41.7"	76°50'53.0"	10	R.C.Thakran	LH, Med.
65.	Kathura-1	29°05'31.2"	76°33'21.2"	4	New	His.
66.	Kathura-2	29°05'00.3"	76°35'36.6"	3	R.C.Thakran	MH, LH.
67.	Kathura-3	29°04'44.6"	76°36'07.0"	3	Silak Ram, R.C.Thakran	His (RW).

68.	Katwal	29°02'35.5"	76°45'19.4"	2	Vinay Kumar	Med.
69.	Kehpa-1	29°07'31.8"	76°34'07.6"	5	New	LH, His, Med.
70.	Kehpa-2	29°07'11.6"	76°35'00.7"	10	R.C.Thakran	LH.
71.	Khandrai	29°09'00.7"	76°41'03.5"	8	R.C.Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
72.	Khanpur Kalan-1	29°10'05.3"	76°48'17.2"	12	Silak Ram, R.C.Thakran, Vinay Kumar	HW, EH, LH, PGW, His (RW, NBPW), Med.
73.	Khanpur Kalan-2	29°09'51.4"	76°49'39.7"	5	New	LH, His (Kusana), Med.
74.	Khanpur Khurd	29°08'15.9"	76°42'08.8"	2	New	His, Med.
75.	Kheri Dankan-1	29°05'48.9"	76°45'27.1"	4	Vinay Kumar	PGW, His, Med.
76.	Kheri Dankan-2	29°05'50.1"	76°46'19.4"	4	Vinay Kumar	LH, His.
77.	Kohla	29°11'17.8"	76°33'57.4"	5	Gujab Singh	LH, GW, His.
78.	Lath	29°05'02.1"	76°46'23.8"	4	Vinay Kumar	His.
79.	Madina	29°05'31.9"	76°39'41.8"	5	New	His, Med.
80.	Mahra	29°05'44.5"	76°40'52.2"	6	R.C.Thakran, Vinay Kumar	LH, His, Med.
81.	Matand	29°15'15.7"	76°42'07.4"	4	New	His, Med.
82.	Mehmudpar-1	29°10'30.7"	76°43'51.1"	6	New	His, Med.
83.	Mehmudpar-2	29°10'58.1"	76°43'16.6"	5	New	His, Med.
84.	Mehmudpur-3	29°11'55.4"	76°41'21.5"	4	Gujab Singh, R.C.Thakran	His (RW) E. Med.
85.	Moi Hooda-1	29°01'28.1"	76°43'38.4"	4	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
86.	Moi Hooda-2	29°03'01.9"	76°43'16.5"	3	Vinay Kumar	Med.
87.	Moi Hooda-3	29°02'23.5"	76°43'14.0"	4	Vinay Kumar	Med.
88.	Mundana-1	29°11'33.4"	76°45'35.1"	4	New	His, Med.
89.	Mundana-2	29°13'49.8"	76°45'25.2"	4	R.C.Thakran	His, Med.
90.	Nagar	29°07'34.1"	76°43'31.0"	4	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
91.	Nait-1	29°07'03.2"	76°46'43.1"	4	Dhankar, Vinay Kumar	LH, His, Med.
92.	Nait-2	29°07'13.8"	76°46'55.9"	2	Vinay Kumar	Med.
93.	Nizampur	29°13'45.8"	76°30'28.4"	4	New	His, Med.
94.	Nuran Khera	29°11'32.4"	76°35'49.0"	3	Dutt, Silak Ram, R.C.Thakran	LH, PGW(BSW), His, Med.
95.	Puthi-1	29°03'40.4"	76°41'57.6"	2	New	Med.
96.	Puthi-2	29°03'36.1"	76°43'10.0"	2	Dhankar, Vinay Kumar	LH, GW, His, Med.
97.	Rabhra	29°04'07.9"	76°43'08.2"	3	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
98.	Rana Kheri	29°16'28.2"	76°36'42.9"	4	New	Med.
99.	Rindhana-1	29°08'46.2"	76°31'04.5"	4	New	His, Med.
100.	Rindhana-2	29°07'16.6"	76°30'02.5"	2	R.C.Thakran	PGW.
101.	Rindhana-3	29°08'00.3"	76°31'35.3"	2	R.C.Thakran	LH.
102.	Rindhana-4	29°08'38.6"	76°31'03.0"	4	Ashok Kumar, Silak Ram, R.C.Thakran	EH, MH, LH.
103.	Rindhana-5	29°03'27.5"	76°31'11.9"	6	Ashok Kumar, R.C.Thakran	EH, LH.
104.	Rukhi-1	29°03'24.8"	76°39'55.3"	6	Sural Bhan, R.C.Thakran, Vinay Kumar	EH, LH, PGW.
105.	Rukhi-2	29°02'54.0"	76°40'29.1"	6	Vinay Kumar	EH, LH, PGW.
106.	Saragthal-1	29°07'19.7"	76°50'15.7"	3	New	His, Med.
107.	Saragthal-2	29°06'51.8"	76°50'06.0"	10	R.C.Thakran, Vinay Kumar	LH, GW, His, Med.
108.	Sikanderpur Mazra	29°06'15.3"	76°44'06.5"	2	New	His, Med.

109	Siwana Mal-1	29°15'27.9"	76°35'28.3"	6	R.C.Thakran	GW, His (RW).
110	Siwana Mal-2	29°14'31.0"	76°34'35.7"	3	Gulab Singh, R.C.Thakran	PGW, His (RW).
111	Siwanka	29°12'21.5"	76°41'32.7"	6	New	His.
112	Shyamni-1	29°11'58.6"	76°49'40.8"	20	Siak R.C.Thakran	LH, OCP, GW, His (RW), Med.
113	Shyamni-2	29°11'16.0"	76°47'29.2"	6	New	LH, His, Med.
114	Thaska	29°06'55.6"	76°40'28.7"	10	New	LMH, LH, His.
115	Thar	29°02'11.5"	76°49'27.1"	2	New	His.

EH= Early Harappan, MH=Mature Harappan, LH=Late Harappan, PGW=Painted Grey Ware, Hist=Historical, Med=Medieval.

Table 2 showing number of sites of different periods

S.no	Period	No of Sites
1	Hakra Ware	01
2	Early Harappan	09
3	Mature Harappan	15
4	Late Harappan	49
5	PGW	27
6	Historical	76
7	Medieval	74

Discussion

The area under study is very rich in archaeological forums. The antiquity of this area can be traced back to proto-historic times. Archaeological explorations have revealed that the earliest settlers in the regions belong to Hakra ware culture. Only a single site Khanpur Kalan-1 belongs to Pre-Harappan period (Ghaggar-Hakra/ Hakra culture) has been reported earlier in the area.^{8, 9, 10} But in the adjoining area a number of sites of late fourth millennium BCE has been reported.^{8, 9, 10}

Hakra ware period

Archaeological explorations have revealed that the earliest settlers in the regions belong to Hakra ware culture. Only one site Khanpur Kalan-1 has been reported earlier by Dr Vinay Kumar in his book¹¹ but the present researcher was unable to find any shard of that period due to soil taken by machines from some part of this site. This type of culture from Cholistan was first mentioned by Mughal companions. Cholistan is a very dry region¹². It was originally watered by a river called Hakra in Pakistan and Gagar Saraswati in India. Some sites from adjoining area comes in the light such as Girawad,¹³ Bhirana,¹⁴ Rakhigarhi,¹⁵ and Kunal.¹⁶ Girawad is just 32 km from the Gohana city so it is very closed to this early reported site.

Early Harappan period

Archaeological explorations have revealed that the next settlers in the regions belong to Early Harappan culture (Sothi-Siswal culture). It is the initial period of the urban phase. Only Nine sites of this period have been explored in the area under present study. The ceramic groups have related with the Sothi-Siswal pottery. The main shapes in this assemblage are jars, vases, bowls, basins and handled pots/basins. There are differences in size but the formal features are more or less the similar. and in the entire ceramic assemblage of Sothi-Siswal bi-chrome sherds are only one or two pieces.

Sothi-Siswal pottery was usually thrown on slow wheel; the rim and neck portion are finished by smoothening with rotation whereas the body portion is finished without rotation as striations and finger impressions of smoothening and scraping are seen on the surface irregular. Usually, the pottery wall usually has a different thickness. The ring base loop-handled pots are very popular¹⁷.

Mature Harappan period

Only fifteen sites have yielded remains of Mature Harappan period. Only a few classical Harappan shapes viz. perforated jar, dish-on-stand vases were recovered from the surface. Some sherds alike to Ganeswar-Jodhpura pottery were also found from the region. Quantity of classical Harappan shapes such as perforated jar, long stem dish-on-stand, beakers, painted jars, nail headed bowls and basins are very less on the surface of the sites. As per earlier explorations report by some researcher we can conclude that as we move south of the study area quantity of classical Harappan pottery reduces.¹⁸

Late Harappan Period

The next cultural phase in the proto-history of this region is distinguished by the Late Harappan culture or degenerate phase of urban Harappans. Forty-nine sites yielded the remains of this phase. The classical Harappan shapes like goblets, perforated jars and classical Harappan paintings fell out of use but some shapes such as beakers, nail headed bowls, dish-on-stands with long stems etc. continue with modifications. The common pottery types are dish-on-stands with ribbed junctions, dish-on-stands with broad and short stands, vases with projected undercut rims, jars with wide and narrow mouths, globular vases with flanged rims, beakers without-turned rims and flasks treated with fine red slip. Out of total 49 Late Harappan sites, six were occupied for the first time, two sites of the Mature Harappan period were preferred by the late Harappan peoples in absence of excavation it is difficult to say that weather there is a cultural break between the Harappans and Late Harappans.¹⁹

Painted Grey Ware Period

During the proto historic period, the last phase is characterized by the advent of the PGW people. The exploration yielded 12 PGW sites. The excavation at Bhagwanpura and Madinaz²⁰ threw light on the relationship between the late Harappan and PGW people

Historical and Medieval period

Eighty sites of historical period were explored. The number of sites indicated that the after 600 BCE the area under present study was thickly populated as compare to proto-historic period. Common shapes of historical pottery were represented by bowls with incurved rim, carinated cooking handis, vases, spouted vases, basins, lid, incense burner. Pottery of later Kushana and Gupta period is less painted as compare to the pottery of Rangmahal, Naurangabad²¹ and Kokhrakakot²² were the regional centers during the historical period. Both areas are located very near to the study area.

Seventy-two sites c; medieval period were explored during the survey. Main shapes include sharp edged bowls, vases, pots etc. a few sherds of glazed ware were also collected during the explorations.

Conclusion

The researchers conducted extensive village-to-village survey in the region and recorded sites with the help of GPS, besides size of settlements and other vital information. This has helped us to correct the earlier recording of sites and their size. Recently some scholars surveyed various parts of Haryana addressing this problem.^{23, 24, 25} Future researchers shall have data on which they can easily bank upon.

During the survey it was noticed that Most of the archaeological sites are either converted into the agriculture fields or the soil is removed for development purpose. The situation is very grim because in a few years it will be very difficult for the archaeologists to spot any site for excavation. Even today it is very hard to spot an intact mound. Hence the present study has its own importance as the sites are now recorded for posterity which may not exist in future.

Acknowledgements

It is my pleasant duty to acknowledge many individuals who enlightened me during my research work such as Profs. Arun Kumar, Dr. Rajpal for their support, valuable suggestions and encouragement. I am grateful to Mr. Mandeeep Bahara, Dr. Vikash Pawar for his keen interest in my research work. I owe sincere thanks to Mr. Samunder for providing me technical support and constant help during the field survey.

References

1. Ram, Sliak (1972). 'Archaeology of Rohtak and Hissar Districts (Haryana)'. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.
2. Suraj, Bhan (1975). 'Prehistoric Archaeology of the Saraswati and Drishadvati Valley (Haryana)'. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, M.S. University Baroda.
3. Dutt, B. (1980). 'Settlements of Painted Grey Ware in Haryana'. Ph.D. Thesis, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.
4. Dhankar (1990). 'History and Archaeology of Gohana Block, District Sonapat, Haryana'. M.Phil. Dissertation, M.D. University, Rohtak.
5. Thakran, R.C. (2000). 'Dynamics of Settlement Archaeology (Haryana)'. Delhi.
6. Kumar, Vinay (2018). 'An Archaeological History of Haryana'. M.Phil. Dissertation (Published), K.U. Kurukshetra.
7. District Sonapat Census Handbook, 1981 & 2011, Chandigarh. P:11.
8. Kumar, Vinay (2018). 'An Archaeological History of Haryana'. M.Phil. Dissertation (Published), K.U. Kurukshetra. P:17-18.
9. Rao, L.S., N.B. Sahu, Prabash Sahu, Samir Diwan and U.A. Shastri (2005). 'New Light on the Excavation of Harappan Settlement at Bhirrana'. Puratatva 35: 60-68.
10. Dangli, Vivek (2007). 'Recent Exploration in Meham, District Rohtak, Haryana'. In Puratatva No. 37:205-212.
11. Kumar, Vinay (2018). 'An Archaeological History of Haryana'. M.Phil. Dissertation (Published), K.U. Kurukshetra. P:17-18
12. Mughal, R. (1982). 'Recent archaeological research cholistan desert. In harappan civilization: a contemporary prespective'. Edited by G.L. Possehl. Oxford & IBH Publishing, New Delhi:85-95.
13. Shinde, V.S. T.Osada, A. Uesugi and Manmohan Kumar (2008). 'Occasional Paper 6, Linguistics Archaeology and Human Past: A Report on Excavations at Farmana 2007-08'. Indus Project, Research Institute for Humanity Nature and Past, Kyoto, Japan. P: 135.
14. Rao, L.S., N.B. Sahu, Prabash Sahu, Samir Diwan and U.A. Shastri (2005). 'New Light on the Excavation of Harappan Settlement at Bhirrana'. in Puratatva no.35: 60-68.
15. Nath, Amarendra (2001). 'Rakhigarhi: 1999-2000'. in Puratatva no.31: 43-46.
16. Khatri, J.S. and M. Acharya (1995). 'Kunal: A New Indus Saraswati Site'. in Puratatva no. 25: 84-86.
17. Dikshit, K.N. (1984). 'The Earliest Pottery in East Asia: A Review with Manjil Hazarika'. Puratatva No. 42: 227-237.
18. Kumar, Manmohan, Akinori Uesugi, V.Shinde, Vivek Dangli, Vijay Kumar, Rajeev Maan and Arun Singh (2011). 'Excavations at Mitthal, District Bhiwani (Haryana) 2010-11: A Preliminary Report'. In Puratatva No.41: 168-178.
19. Kumar, Manmohan, Akinori Uesugi, V.Shinde, Vivek Dangli, Vijay Kumar, Rajeev Maan and Arun Singh (2011). 'Excavations at Mitthal, District Bhiwani (Haryana) 2010-11: A Preliminary Report'. In Puratatva No.41: 168-178.
20. Kumar, Manmohan (2009). 'Harappan Settlements in the Ghaggar-Yamuna Divide, in Occasional Paper 7: Linguistics, Archaeology and the Human Past (T. Osada and Akinori Uesugi Eds.)'. Kyoto: Indus Project. pp 1-78.
21. Sanger, P.B.S. (2005). 'Excavations at Naurangabad-Haryana (2000-01)'. Puratatva 35:191-195.
22. Kumar, Manmohan (1996). 'Ancient Mint at Rohtak'. In K.K. Maheswari and Biswajeet Path (eds.). Numismatic Panorama, Harman Publish House, New Delhi.
23. Dangli, Vivek (2007). 'Recent Exploration in Meham, District Rohtak', Haryana. In Puratatva No. 37:205-212.
24. Singh, R.N., C.A. Petrie, V.Pawar, A.K. Pandey, S.Neogi, M.Singh, A.K. Singh, D. Parik and C. Lancelotti (2010). 'Changing Patterns of Settlements in the Rise and Fall of Harappan Urbanism and Beyond: A Preliminary Report on the Rakhigarhi Hinterland Survey 2009'. Man and Environment XXXV (1):37-53).
25. Singh, R.N., C.A. Petrie, V.Pawar, A.K.Pandey and D. Parikh (2011). 'New Light onto Settlement along the river Ghaggar and its Hinterland: A Preliminary Report on the Ghaggar Hinterland Survey 2010'. Man and Environment XXXVI (2):88-106.